

THE ROLE OF PUBLIC CONTROL IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ELECTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article describes the electoral system in Uzbekistan and the role of public control in the implementation of democratic elections.

Keywords: Constitution, democracy, legal norm, law, civil society, electoral system, public control.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада Ўзбекистонда сайлов тизими ва демократик сайловларни амалга оширишда жамоатчилик назоратини ўрни ёритилган. Калит сўзлар: Конституция, демократия, ҳуқуқий норма, қонун, фуқоралик жамияти, сайлов тизими, жамоатчилик назорати.

Аннотация: В данной статье описывается избирательная система Узбекистана и роль общественного контроля в проведении демократических выборов.

Ключевые слова: Конституция, демократия, правовая норма, право, гражданское общество, избирательная система, общественный контроль.

The establishment of a democratic legal state and an open civil society is inextricably linked with the implementation of the constitutional principle of people's power and the necessary conditions for holding democratic elections under public control. Elections are an important institution of modern democracy, one of the main means by which people express their will and participate in political processes, management of society and state affairs, including the formation of representative bodies of power. Free elections are not only a principle of formation of the government, but also an expression of its responsibility to the people. The formation of the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its activities are governed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On the Election of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On the Election to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "People's Deputies of Regions, Districts and Cities" It is regulated by the provisions of the law on elections to councils. In particular, Article 117 of our Constitution establishes the procedure for the formation of the Central Election Commission, as well as the fact that its activities are based on the principles of independence, legality, collegiality, transparency and fairness.[1]

These principles were reflected in the Law “On the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan”. In accordance with it, the Central Election Commission and its members perform their activities independently of any state bodies, public associations and officials. The members of the Central Election Commission express their opinion free from political biases and other foreign influences when making decisions.[2]

This ensures impartiality in the activity of the Central Election Commission. One of the important principles of the activity of the Central Election Commission is openness. Meetings of the Central Election Commission are held in public. Implementation of this principle allows representatives of political parties, mass media, observers from other countries, international organizations and movements to be present at the meetings of the Central Election Commission. According to Article 21 of the Law “On the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan” adopted in a new version on June 25, 2019, the Central Election Commission and its members perform their activities independently of any state bodies, public associations and officials. In addition, one of the important factors determining the independence of the Central Election Commission is the provision of administrative responsibility for illegal interference in its activities, non-execution of its decisions. These norms create a basis for the Central Election Commission to carry out its activities free from external influences, to strengthen its activities in the way of effectively ensuring the electoral rights of citizens.[3]

The constitution establishes a democratic procedure for the election of members of the Central Election Commission by the people's representatives, and the executive bodies do not participate in this process at all. In particular, in accordance with Article 3 of the Law “On the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, the members of the Central Election Commission are elected by the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the recommendation of the Dzhokorgi Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, People’s Deputies of the Regions and Tashkent City Councils.[4]

The Chairman of the Central Election Commission is elected from among the members of the commission at the meeting of the commission on the recommendation of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, the deputy chairman of the Central Election Commission and the secretary of the commission are elected from among the members of the commission at the commission meeting. These are also additional legal guarantees that ensure the

independence of the Central Election Commission. District and precinct election commissions also play an important role in the election process. A total of 971 international observers, including nearly two dozen prestigious international organizations, including the OSCE Parliamentary Assembly and Bureau for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization and other international organizations, a total of 631 observers, 50 of the world's 50 340 international observers from about This also means that international organizations are very interested in this year's elections in Uzbekistan.[5]

Of course, no matter how democratic the state power is, it is not fully covered by the entire population of the country. State power is exercised by a separate apparatus. The democracy of the state is assessed depending on the state of participation of the people (its representatives) in its formation and organization of its activities. Here, on December 22, 2019, New Uzbekistan. Let's dwell on how effectively public control was organized and successfully implemented in the elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local councils of People's Deputies held at a high level under the slogan "New elections". First of all, in accordance with the requirements of the country's election legislation, in all activities related to the preparation and conduct of the election, as well as in the polling booths and counting of votes on the election day, observers from political parties that nominated candidates for deputies, citizens' self-government bodies, representatives of the mass media, from other countries, there is a rule that observers from international organizations have the right to participate.[6]

In accordance with this rule, among the representatives of political parties, other countries and international organizations that nominated candidates for deputies, for the first time in the national election practice of our country, representatives of citizens' self-governing bodies are also allowed to participate in all activities related to the preparation and conduct of the election, as well as in the voting booths and counting of votes on the election day. given the right to appoint an observer for participation. According to the decision of the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 951 dated October 5, 2019, the Regulation on Observers from Political Parties and Citizens' Self-Governing Bodies was approved. According to this Regulation, the chairman (elder) of the citizens' assembly, his deputy, adviser, as well as other officials of the citizens' assembly bodies, may be observers from the citizens' self-management bodies. The purpose of monitoring is to exercise public control

over the observance of election legislation in all activities related to the preparation and conduct of the election, including voting and counting of votes on the election day. If we pay attention to the statistical data of the Central Election Commission, in the elections held on December 22, 2019, 10,250 polling stations were established in the territory of our country. Also, 55 polling stations were established at the embassies and diplomatic missions of our country in foreign countries, and in almost all of these polling stations, more than ten thousand observers from citizens' self-governance bodies carried out public control effectively.

In particular, they are present at meetings of election commissions; participation in meetings dedicated to the nomination of candidates, meetings of candidates with voters; to be present at the polling station, to observe the progress of preparatory work, the placement of secret voting booths or rooms and the sealing of ballot boxes, the registration of citizens, the delivery of ballot papers to them; monitoring the voting process on election day; to be informed about the time and place of early voting and to monitor this process; monitoring the voting process at the voter's location with his permission; to be present when the votes are counted and the report of the election commission is drawn up; request and receive copies of the documents on election results certified by the relevant election commission; making photo, video, audio recordings without violating the secrecy of the election process and voting; contact media representatives about the results of surveillance; to receive reports on the results of vote counting from precinct election commissions by the district election commission and to be present in the process of determining election results by district; effectively used their rights reflected in the national election legislation, such as expressing their opinion on electoral legislation, as well as preparing for and conducting the election. Above, we drew attention to the fact that, for the first time in the practice of national elections, along with representatives of political parties, other countries and international organizations, representatives of self-governing bodies of citizens were given the right to appoint an observer to prepare for the election and participate in all activities related to its holding. So what is the need for this? What is the difference between observers of citizens' self-government bodies and observers of political parties or foreign countries and international organizations nominated by candidates? It is natural that everyone is interested in such questions. First of all, we think that it is necessary to pay attention to the content and purpose of the observation and the observer. Because any observation directly depends on its purpose. In our opinion,

observers from foreign countries and international organizations should first of all check the extent to which the political rights of citizens (voting and being elected) are ensured in the elections organized in the country, the requirements of the international law norms and standards for conducting democratic elections of the national election legislation and practice, and the practice of developed legal democracies. focuses on monadity. Their composition will consist of representatives of various prestigious international organizations and many foreign countries.

Public oversight is a mechanism for the application and implementation of laws and decisions of public authorities in the person of individual citizens and through civil society institutions, as well as the evaluation of the results of these processes.[7]

Observers of political parties are primarily interested in protecting the interests of the political party that appointed them as observers in these elections and the persons nominated by this political party as candidates for deputy. They make their observations primarily based on this goal. Observers of citizens' self-governance bodies are an independent institution of civil society, independent of the various levels of election commissions responsible for organizing and holding elections, as well as political parties that have the right to nominate candidates for deputies. Simply put, people's representatives who act in the interest of the electorate. It is no exaggeration to say that during the elections, they effectively exercised public control over the activities of election commissions, over the activities of political parties, and over the behavior of candidates for deputy. Observers of self-government bodies of citizens who are subjects of public control during election processes can effectively carry out public control in three directions: first, choosing buildings for polling stations, equipping polling stations, forming the composition of election commissions, drawing up the list of voters; secondly, the selection of candidates for deputy by political parties, formalization of their documents, submission to election commissions, examination of documents of these candidates by election commissions, registration of candidates for deputy, holding meetings with voters by candidates for deputy, conducting election campaign, appearing in mass media; thirdly, through active participation in important processes such as equipping polling stations by precinct election commissions, organizing and conducting the voting process, including early voting, ensuring the voting rights of voters at their places of residence, issuing voting results, and correctly drawing up reports implemented effective public control.[8]

In short, to further increase the role of the institution of observers from citizens' self-governing bodies in the upcoming elections, to further strengthen their knowledge of national and international election legislation, democratic election standards and electoral practice, and to ensure that they effectively exercise public control over the election process - the organization of future elections at a higher level will give its positive result if it is conducted in an open, transparent and transparent manner.

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